

Obituary

In Memory of Prof. Dr. Maria Santos Bruzón Gallego

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It is with great sadness that we write this memoriam for our beloved friend and colleague Maria de los Santos Bruzón who was an editor of this Special Issue. For us and for all her friends, she was affectionately Maruchi. She was born in Cádiz Spain in 1956, and she passed away in Sevilla Spain in September 2021.

She received her PhD from the University of Cádiz in 2000. Subsequently, she was an assistant professor and full professor at the University of Cádiz. In addition, she held several positions at the university administration, such as Vice-Dean and Director of the Unity of University Quality, and lately, she was head of the Mathematics Department and main researcher of her research group.

Professor Bruzón was a passionate researcher and hard worker. She published countless articles mainly in symmetry groups and their applications to partial and ordinary differential equations, conservation laws, and direct methods to find exact solutions for partial differential equations with physical, biological, engineering, or medical interest. Her papers have been published in very high-rank journals, with more than 1300 cites and index h 19.

Professor Bruzón also attended a large number of conferences all around the world (several of them organized by herself) in order to disseminate her research.

She also established collaborations with colleagues around the world. She was visiting professor in several universities. In particular, together with ML Gandarias, she was a visiting researcher at the University of Catania several times, building with us a fruitful scientific collaboration and a deep, strong friendship.

During her career, Professor Bruzón supervised many MA and PhD students and postdocs. She was an adviser for more than six PhD students.

Maruchi was also well known for her generosity; she was always happy to make time for everyone and to share her ideas. She created opportunities for students and junior researchers.

Maruchi was a talented mathematician, but she was also extremely kind, ap-proachable, and wonderful to work with. In all, she was a role model for many of us—as a researcher but also as a person.

For us, she was a very close friend and collaborator, always approachable when we needed her, and funny; we spent a lot of time working, travelling, and enjoying ourselves together. For us, it is a great loss, and we miss and will miss her always.

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